

Correspondence on “Short Communication: Reduced GBLUP equations to core animals in the algorithm for proven and young (APY)”—Simplifications when non-core animals are non-phenotyped

Mohammad Ali Nilforooshan*

Livestock Improvement Corporation, Private Bag 3016, Hamilton 3240, New Zealand

Abstract: The Algorithm for Proven and Young (APY) enables scalable genomic evaluation by approximating the inverse of the genomic relationship matrix through partitioning genotyped animals into core and non-core groups. A recently published short communication showed that, under APY, genomic BLUP (GBLUP) can be reduced to a system of equations involving only core animals, with solutions for non-core animals obtained by back-solving. In this correspondence, I demonstrate that when the non-core group contains no phenotyped animals, this reduced-equivalent GBLUP formulation can be further simplified. Under this condition, several matrix derivations and calculations become unnecessary, and the back-solving of non-core solutions is considerably simplified.

Keywords: APY, core, non-core, GBLUP, back-solve

1. Introduction

The number of genotypes in many livestock populations has reached millions. In genomic animal models, such as genomic BLUP (GBLUP) and single-step GBLUP (ss-GBLUP), the inverse of the genomic relationship matrix (\mathbf{G}) is required. In GBLUP, only genotyped animals are evaluated, whereas in ssGBLUP both genotyped and non-genotyped animals are evaluated simultaneously. Inverting \mathbf{G} becomes a computational bottleneck when the number of genotyped animals exceeds 150K (Bradford et al., 2017; Fragomeni et al., 2015; Misztal, 2016). The Algorithm for Proven and Young (APY; Misztal et al., 2014) overcomes this limitation by dividing genotyped animals into core (c) and non-core (n) groups and approximating \mathbf{G}^{-1} based on \mathbf{G}_{cc}^{-1} (\mathbf{G}_{APY}^{-1}). This makes genomic evaluation of large genotyped populations feasible at a lower computational cost.

In APY, the breeding values of non-core animals are conditioned to the breeding values of core animals. Nilforooshan (2024) exploited this conditionality and developed a reduced system of GBLUP equations for core animals, equivalent to the full GBLUP model. After solving the GBLUP equations for core

animals, solutions for non-core animals are back-solved.

The aim of this correspondence is to present simplifications to the method of Nilforooshan (2024) when the non-core group contains no phenotyped animals.

2. Methods

The mixed model equations for the reduced-equivalent GBLUP developed by Nilforooshan (2024) are:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{X}'\mathbf{R}^{-1}\mathbf{X} & \mathbf{X}'\mathbf{R}^{-1}\mathbf{W} \\ \mathbf{W}'\mathbf{R}^{-1}\mathbf{X} & \mathbf{W}'\mathbf{R}^{-1}\mathbf{W} + \mathbf{G}_{cc}^{-1}\lambda \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{b}} \\ \hat{\mathbf{a}}_c \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{X}'\mathbf{R}^{-1}\mathbf{y} \\ \mathbf{W}'\mathbf{R}^{-1}\mathbf{y} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{y} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{y}_c \\ \mathbf{y}_n \end{bmatrix}$, $\mathbf{W} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{z}_c \\ \mathbf{z}_n^* \end{bmatrix}$, $\mathbf{R}^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_c & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{R}^{nn} \end{bmatrix}$, \mathbf{I}_c is an identity matrix of the size c , and $\mathbf{R}^{nn} = (\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{D}_{nn}/\lambda)^{-1}$. In his article, he presented the equations for \mathbf{Z}_n^* and \mathbf{D}_{nn} . He denoted non-genotyped and genotyped animals with 1 and 2, respectively. Since GBLUP is limited to genotyped animals, the index 2 is omitted here for simplicity. When the non-core group is free from phenotyped animals, Eq. 1 simplifies considerably to:

*Corresponding author: mohammad.nilforooshan@lic.co.nz

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{X}'\mathbf{X} & \mathbf{X}'\mathbf{Z}_c \\ \mathbf{Z}'_c\mathbf{X} & \mathbf{Z}'_c\mathbf{Z}_c + \mathbf{G}_{cc}^{-1}\lambda \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{b}} \\ \hat{\mathbf{a}}_c \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{X}'\mathbf{y}_c \\ \mathbf{Z}'_c\mathbf{y}_c \end{bmatrix}, (2)$$

and the derivation of \mathbf{Z}_n^* and \mathbf{D}_{nn} , as well as the calculation of \mathbf{R}^{nn} , are no longer required.

Nilforooshan (2024) presented the equations for back-solving the solutions of non-core animals ($\hat{\mathbf{a}}_n$) from $\hat{\mathbf{a}}_c$, directly and independently for non-core phenotyped and non-core non-phenotyped animals. Back-solving the solutions for non-core non-phenotyped animals is straightforward and considerably simpler. As such, where the non-core group is free from phenotyped animals, the back-solving of solutions for non-core animals also simplifies to:

$$\hat{\mathbf{a}}_n = \mathbf{G}_{nc}\mathbf{G}_{cc}^{-1}\hat{\mathbf{a}}_c. (3)$$

Notably, there is no need to calculate \mathbf{G}_{nn} , or even the diagonal approximation of \mathbf{G}^{nn} (block of \mathbf{G}^{-1} corresponding to n) in the APY algorithm.

3. Discussion

When the number of phenotyped animals is limited ($< 150\text{K}$), excluding phenotyped animals from the non-core group considerably simplifies the reduced-equivalent GBLUP analysis and its following back-solving. Note that making the non-core group free from phenotyped animals is not equivalent to limiting the core group to phenotyped animals, and the core group can include non-phenotyped animals that are not in the non-core group.

Previous studies have reported that a core group with a random sample of animals performs well as it covers different generations (Bradford et al., 2017; Ostersen et al., 2016). Including phenotyped animals in the core group does not conflict with representing multiple generations in the core group, except in the case of novel traits, where phenotyped animals may be concentrated in the most recent generations. If phenotyped animals do not have representatives in different generations, non-phenotyped animals can represent the less represented generations in the core group.

Finally, if the large number of genotyped animals prevents their full inclusion in the core group, increasing their proportion in the core group still provides computational advantages for the reduced-equivalent GBLUP model and subsequent back-solving.

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